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Rural Science-Society-Policy
Interfaces

D7.6 SYNTHESIS OUTPUTS ADAPTED FOR CITIZEN AUDIENCES

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Table of Contents

Acronyms	iv
Executive Summary	v
1. Introduction	1
2. Engagement Strategy and Approach	1
3. Materials Developed for Citizen Engagement	2
3.1 Synoptic PowerPoints.....	2
3.2 Videos	3
3.3 Storymap	6
3.4 Virtual Reality Demonstration Model.....	7
3.5 Fiches on Governance of Rural Areas	9
4. Example Activities with Citizens	10
4.1 Conference of the Parties (COP) 26.....	11
4.2 European and National Rural Parliaments	12
4.3 European Week of Regions and Cities	13
4.4 Education.....	14
4.5 Events Organised With and Through Civil Society and MAPs.....	15
4.6 Broadcast and Digital Media	18
5. Conclusions	18
6. Acknowledgments	20
7. References	21

Acronyms

COP	Convention of the Parties
COVID-19	Coronavirus 19
EC	European Commission
ECRA	European Rural Community Alliance
EEA	European Environment Agency
ERDN	European Rural Development Network
ERP	European Rural Parliament
EU	European Union
EWRC	European Week of Regions and Cities
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
LTVRA	Long Term Vision for Rural Areas
MAP	Multi-Actor Platform
MSP	Member of the Scottish Parliament
NGO	Non-governmental Organisation
NTS	National Trust for Scotland
Q&A	Question and Answer
SHERPA	Sustainable Hub to Engage into Rural Policies with Actors
UK	United Kingdom
UNECE	United Nations Economic Commission for Europe

Executive Summary

The principle that EU institutions should engage citizens in formulation of future policies is enshrined in Article 11(1) of the Treaty on European Union, “the institutions shall, by appropriate means, give citizens and representative associations the opportunity to make known and publicly exchange their views in all areas of Union action” ([European Union, 2012](#)). The Long Term Vision for Rural Areas (LTVRA) ([European Commission, 2021a](#)) recognises that “delivering on the goals of the Vision and adapting to changing economic and social realities can only be done in cooperation with citizens living in rural areas.”

An aim of SHERPA, in response to the requirement in the call for tenders, was to enable citizens, researchers and policymakers from European regions to engage in dialogue for the formulation of concrete proposals on future rural policies. The SHERPA strategy for engaging with the wider public was one of a twin track of developing complementary activities at local and EU levels, through civil society groups, and by direct engagement. To deliver this strategy, resources were developed centrally and used locally through the project partners or MAPs, and developed locally, cognisant of specific issues and sensitivities. The range of contents and messages cover all four of the pillars of the Rural Action Plan of **Stronger, Connected, Resilient** and **Prosperous**, and some items directly relate to some of building blocks of the Rural Action Plan (e.g. peatland restoration and carbon farming).

The principal sets of materials which were developed for citizen engagement were: i) five synoptic PowerPoint presentations, developed to provide insights to some of the issues covered by the SHERPA MAPs and SHERPA level position papers; ii) a series of videos, developed for audiences with a non-technical background produced for events such as the [3rd Citizen Engagement and Deliberative Democracy Festival](#), COP26, and some led by individual partners (e.g. CONSULAI); iii) a storymap, to support explanations of issues relating to climate change and land use impacting on rural areas; iv) interactive virtual reality demonstration models, for two-way sharing knowledge, between citizens and the SHERPA teams, of approaches to tackling climate change and environmental sustainability through land use management practices; v) fiches on the governance of rural areas by each of the MAPs, and (vi) a SHERPA final message video. These media and channels of communication developed complement those used to scientific and policy audiences such as conference presentations and proceedings, journal papers, and briefings of various forms.

Citizen engagement tools were used in citizen engagement activities at international and national levels, such as: i) the Conference of the Parties 26, at which SHERPA ran a live panel moderated Q&A session on ‘How rural areas can contribute to a just transition to climate neutrality’, and a stand in the Green Zone open to members of the public; ii) the European rural parliament, in 2021 and 2022, and national rural parliaments, such as in Finland and Scotland, UK; iii) European Week of Regions and Cities, with sessions such as [Effective Mechanisms To Address New Governance Challenges In European Rural Areas](#), in 2022, and Participatory lab on the emancipation of rural areas in regional and urban policy, in 2023; iv) education, with contributions to school and university courses, such as visions of rural areas by 2050 in Keil, Germany; v) events organised with and through civil society at local to national levels; and vi) broadcast media.

The materials designed primarily for citizen engagement provide a valuable set of legacy materials that can be expanded upon as contexts evolve (e.g. storymap, virtual reality models, videos) and used at levels from European, national down to local as appropriate. Several items (e.g. fiches on governance, videos, and broadcast media) are in languages other than English.

The processes of citizen engagement exposed partners to perspectives, evidence, suggestions, criticisms, and feedback on recommendations which are not otherwise captured within the network of MAPs. That was part of a structured, bottom-up approach to the preparation of Position Papers, and ultimately the sets of recommendations for future policies and research.

The processes and outputs of the SHERPA science-society-policy interfaces facilitated pertinent contributions of citizens into policy making. The significance of such perspectives and inputs is reflected in the [European](#)

[Commission \(2020\)](#) observation that “the volatility of evidence, uncertainty of today and tomorrow’s facts requires mobilising all citizens to share not only relevant knowledge but also responsibility on the governance of the current crises.”

1. Introduction

The principle that EU institutions should engage citizens in formulation of future policies is enshrined in Article 11(1) of the Treaty on European Union, “the institutions shall, by appropriate means, give citizens and representative associations the opportunity to make known and publicly exchange their views in all areas of Union action” ([European Union, 2012](#)). Citizen participation in public discourse and decision-making is also a principle of the Aarhus Convention to which the EU is a signatory ([UNECE, 1998](#)). It was reiterated in the Political Guidelines of the European Commission (2019-2024) in which President Ursula von der Leyen established a political priority of “a new push for European democracy” with a commitment to “strengthen the links between people, nations and institutions” ([von der Leyen, 2019](#)).

The aims of the Long Term Vision for Rural Areas (LTVRA) and its Rural Action Plan is for stronger, connected, resilient and prosperous rural areas by 2040 ([European Commission, 2021a](#)). It recognises that “delivering on the goals of the Vision and adapting to changing economic and social realities can only be done in cooperation with citizens living in rural areas.” This cooperation may be reflected directly through the uptake of training and education opportunities (in **Stronger**, and **Prosperous** pillars of the Rural Action Plan), actions to restore peatland or citizen-led initiatives to tackle climate change (in the **Resilient** pillar) or taking responsibilities through LEADER/CLLD under the **Stronger** pillar. Indirect support can be exercised through governance mechanisms such as elections to representative bodies or taking responsibilities in civil society groups (Vilcu *et al.*, 2023; SHERPA [Empowering rural areas in multi-level governance processes](#)), enabling directing of some financial resources or legislative initiatives.

An aim of SHERPA, in response to the requirement in the call for tenders, was to enable citizens, researchers and policymakers from European regions to engage in dialogue for the formulation of concrete proposals on future rural policies. This was to include discussions at regional (including locally specific engagement), national and EU levels. The SHERPA multi-level [multi-actor platforms](#) (MAPs) provided forums for an ongoing process of exchanging ideas for the co-learning and co-creation of knowledge at European and regional levels, formalised as science-policy-society interfaces ([Slatmo *et al.*, 2021, D5.1](#); [Potters *et al.*, 2023, D6.4](#)). It used the LTVRA as a framework for developing recommendations for policies ([Chartier *et al.*, 2021](#); [Chartier *et al.*, 2023](#); D7.5), and research ([Miller *et al.*, 2023a](#)). This Deliverable provides examples of the materials developed and their means of deployment for reaching out to citizens audiences, and how they link to the pillars of the LTVRA.

2. Engagement Strategy and Approach

The SHERPA strategy for engaging with citizens of Europe has been one of a twin track of developing complementary activities at local and EU levels, and through civil society groups and direct engagement. The aim was to support and facilitate engagement with citizens alongside and via the SHERPA process of MAPs at regional, national and EU levels.

The purpose of the engagement was to augment the topics for consideration in the MAPs, share evidence compiled in SHERPA Discussion Papers, and recommendations in Position Papers. Materials used with public audiences were developed to synthesise findings on the topics considered by the MAPs, particularly those local to the audience, or at a project level ([Chartier *et al.*, 2023](#); D7.5).

Resources have been developed by the project centrally and used at European and national levels through, for example, institutions such as the European Rural Parliament (ERP), and developed locally, cognisant of specific issues and sensitivities, for use within local contexts. Materials were developed for deployment in a variety of media and environments such as audio-visual presentations and virtual reality facilities. These resources and channels of communication complement those used to scientific and policy audiences such as conference presentations and proceedings, journal papers, and briefings of various forms.

The types of materials developed for collecting views and sharing information about rural issues and recommendations for future policies and research evolved through the project as opportunities and technical options arose. Each MAP and project partner contributed to those materials and associated activities, aligning content and messages in ways most relevant their local audiences, or at regional or European levels where within their remits.

The nature of civil society organisations involved in the MAPs encompasses a broad range of interests and forms of governance. Their roles and the nature of their membership provided different types of pathways of information flow, active (e.g. hands-on exhibits and workshops), and passive (e.g. viewing videos or presentations). The SHERPA approach was to work with such organisations to identify opportunities where topics, remits and timescales aligned. An advantage to SHERPA was in attracting audiences, online and in situ, sharing resources (personnel and financial), amplifying messages about recommendations, and building legacies of new or improved relationships. From the perspectives of some civil society groups, there are similar types of advantages, and one of being able to demonstrate communication channels through to higher levels of governance (e.g. to public agencies, policy interests and businesses at regional, national and EU levels).

Direct engagement was undertaken by partners, usually in collaboration with national and regional MAPs. The nature of the opportunity reflects the remits and composition of the partner and MAPs, with some having member organisations or individuals with business or voluntary roles in engaging with citizen audiences. A range of channels were used, both *in situ* and online, and in different formats which included partner organised exhibitions and presentations, and online and analogue tools and materials. Direct engagement also includes conventional and digital mass media (e.g. radio, television), requiring reaching out to broadcasters and designing the publicising of the project so as to attract attention of media and journalists.

An overview follows of the materials developed (Section 3) and means of engagement (Section 4) with citizen audiences, directly or through representatives.

3. Materials Developed for Citizen Engagement

Resources have been developed which are central to the SHERPA project and used locally through the project partners or MAPs. The types of materials developed for collecting views and sharing information about rural issues and recommendations for future policies and research have evolved through the project as opportunities and technical options arose. Each MAP and project partner contributed to those materials and associated activities, aligning content and messages in ways most relevant their local audiences, or at regional or European levels where within their remits. The principal set of centrally developed resources are summarised below, followed by examples of the types of events at which citizen audience were engaged, at project or MAP levels.

3.1 Synoptic PowerPoints

A set of synoptic PowerPoints was developed to provide insights to some of the issues covered by the SHERPA MAPs. These topics were [Climate Change and Land Use](#), [Digitalisation in Rural Areas](#), [Empowering Rural Areas in Multi-Level Governance Processes](#), [Social Dimension of Rural Areas](#), and [Sustainable and Resilient value chains](#).

These presentations were developed from the relevant SHERPA level discussion and position papers, covering a total of five topics, and high level examples of existing practices drawn from position papers of individual regional or national MAPs. Materials for the PowerPoints were drawn from a total of 33 position and discussion papers from 29 different MAPs, with links to the relevant papers. As such they provide additional profile for individual MAPs and a mechanism for conveying a set of specific messages from bottom-up sources. The presentations were first used at the [SHERPA Final Conference](#), 1st and 2nd June 2023, and subsequently as

display materials for audiences at public events (e.g. [Scotland’s Rural and Islands Parliament](#), Fort William, UK, November 2023).

Figure 1 illustrates examples of the overview of material contributing to the topics of two of the synoptic PowerPoints, on Sustainable and Resilient Value Chains (Position Paper, [Bognar and Schwarz, 2023](#)) (Figure 1 a, b), and Climate Change and Land Use (Position Paper, [Miller et al., 2023](#)) (Figure 1 c, d).

Figure 1 (a). Synoptic PowerPoint on Sustainable and Resilient Value Chains; slide summarising SHERPA level discussion and position papers, and the 13 contributing regional and national MAPs and their position papers.

Figure 1 (b). Slide summarising three examples of good practices relating to sustainable supply chains highlighted by regional and national MAPs, with links to the relevant position papers.

Figure 1 (c). Synoptic PowerPoint on Climate change and land use; slide summarising SHERPA level discussion and position papers, and the 18 contributing regional and national MAPs and their position papers.

Figure 1 (d). Slide summarising three examples of good practices tackling climate change highlighted by regional and national MAPs, with links to the relevant position papers.

3.2 Videos

A series of videos has been developed for use with all audience types, but predominantly those with a non-technical background. They cover topics of relevance to the people and places of rural Europe, and of the process of SHERPA in developing bottom up positions and recommendations for policy and research.

Several such videos were developed to aid communicate the messages from SHERPA MAPs at high profile international and European events, such as SHERPA at the [3rd Citizen Engagement and Deliberative Democracy Festival](#) (Figure 2), and [SHERPA at the Convention of the Parties 26 \(COP26\)](#) (Figure 3). For both events SHERPA submitted applications for inclusion in the programmes which were subsequently accepted, in each case preparing videos for use at the event and as a legacy to use with wider audiences.

An aim of the [3rd Citizen Engagement and Deliberative Democracy Festival](#) was to advance “the talk (and walk) about mainstreaming citizen engagement and deliberation in policy matters in the Commission in particular, and within public administration in general” ([European Commission, 2020](#)). The SHERPA video contributed to the citizen engagement festival and was designed to explain the opportunities for using science, society and policy interfaces, in the form of Multi-Actor Platforms in co-constructing visions for rural areas. In the programme, the SHERPA video was played in support of the early stages of widening citizen engagement in development of the Long Term Vision for Rural Areas, introducing the session on “Welcome to our rural! Citizen engagement in developing a long term vision for rural areas”, presented by Zélie Peppiette, EC-AGRI (10th December 2020).

The messages from the MAP members at regional, national and EU levels, highlighted how citizens and their representatives can be brought into a wider process of developing visions for rural areas of Europe, complementing other approaches in the portfolio being deployed or facilitated by the European Commission (e.g. to develop the Research and Development of the Horizon Europe Missions). Amongst key requirements for such a process was developing trust between actors, such as those making the decisions and those who have to implement them on the ground, and capabilities and frameworks that enable communication between parties *“in the right place, at the right time, to the right people in the right way”* (L. Dawson, UK MAP).

The video prepared for use on the SHERPA exhibit at [COP 26](#) in November 2021 (Glasgow, UK; Section 4.1) involved members of MAPs from four countries, including both of the co-host countries of the COP26 (Italy and the United Kingdom). Contributors provided perspectives on issues relating to mitigating or adapting to climate change identified by their MAPs (Figure 3, a to f). The content of those messages also formed elements of the [SHERPA Position Paper on Climate Change and Environmental Sustainability](#) (Miller *et al.*, 2022a). Extracts of the video were also used at other public events around COP26, such as the 43rd TB Macaulay Lecture on outrage and optimism in the face of the climate crisis (Glasgow, 2nd November 2021), and is available on the [SHERPA Youtube channel](#).

<p>Figure 3 (a). SHERPA video for COP 26, recommending a place-based approach to identifying solutions that tackle climate change.</p>	<p>Figure 3 (b). Pedro Santos, ConsulAI, partner and facilitator Southwest Alentejo Portugal MAP recommending research into soils and permanent crops as carbon sinks (Dias et al., 2022).</p>
<p>Figure 3 (c). Olga Kriezi, South Aegean Greece MAP recommending mandatory adoption of environmental measures.</p>	<p>Figure 3 (d). Emilia Pellegrini, U. Bologna, partner and monitor Emilia-Romagna Italy MAP the aim of reducing energy consumption.</p>
<p>Figure 3 (e). Lorna Dawson, Rural Scotland UK MAP recommending getting communities to work together to create solutions.</p>	<p>Figure 3 (f). SHERPA video for COP 26, recommending policy attention is paid to human well-being and mental health in relation to impacts of climate change.</p>

Video resources have also been created on specific themes triggered by third party events such as the EU AgriResearch Conference 2023 for which they invited nine projects to have videos created to convey their opinions on [What's next for EU agriculture?](#); Figure 4 a, b). The [AgriResearch Conference](#) brought together researchers, farmers, rural communities, industry, advisors, policymakers, citizens and NGO representatives to discuss how research and innovation can tackle the challenges faced by agriculture, forestry and rural areas, and to identify what new opportunities should be explored. Subsequently, the SHERPA video was available for use with citizen and stakeholder audiences for promoting the project alongside others funded by the European Union, and as support for events run for rural stakeholder groups.

Some MAPs created their own videos, motivated by specific debates or as part of their portfolio of communication tailored for use with local actors. For example, CONSULAI prepared a video on [The future](#)

[challenges of rural areas](#), created at the AGROGLOBAL show (September 2023). This involved contributions from municipalities (e.g. Santarém City Council; Fundão City Council) and representatives from agricultural sectors (e.g. Alentejana Regional Wine Commission; Association of Horticulturists, Fruit Growers and Floriculturists in Odemira and Aljezur). The content helps explain to consumers and practitioners of some of the issues being faced by rural areas from the perspectives of particular sectors (Figure 4 c, d).

3.3 Storymap

A storymap was prepared to provide materials that support explanations of issues relating to climate change and land use affecting rural areas, and recommendations from SHERPA for policy and research, for use in different environments. The content was drawn from the relevant discussion and position papers, and materials prepared for use on the SHERPA [COP26 exhibit](#) in the Green Zone for public visitors.

Materials were provided by members of SHERPA MAPs and bringing together key messages for policy and research from SHERPA Position and Discussion Papers on climate change and environmental sustainability ([Miller et al., 2022a](#)), and Climate change and land use ([Miller et al., 2023a](#)), and the UK Position Paper on climate change and environmental sustainability ([Miller et al., 2022b](#)). Topics include examples of issues faced by rural areas due to climate change such as pressures on primary production, and transport and housing infrastructure, and social issues such as mental health and human well-being, accentuated by pressures of climate change.

Recommendations communicated include approaches to mitigating or adapting to climate change such as restoring peatland areas through carbon farming, managing soils, both building blocks of the pillar of **Resilient** rural areas, and monitoring land characteristics using ground based sensors, a building block in line with the pillar of **Connected** rural areas.

The approach used the [ESRI ArcGIS Storymap](#) system. This enables the incorporation of multimedia materials (e.g. videos, audio, maps, images) into a narrative. This included slides compiled for relevant PowerPoint presentations, videos provided by members of MAPs (e.g. Figure 5a), and links to online map-based information from organisations such as the European Environment Agency (EEA) (e.g. Figure 5b). This enables the storymap to take advantage of a broad set of supporting evidence and materials, and the functionality of the multiple sources of media by which they have been made available.

The prototype storymap was used at public events around COP26, such as the 43rd TB Macaulay Lecture on outrage and optimism in the face of the climate crisis (Glasgow, 2nd November 2021), and refined with additional materials from SHERPA position Papers. Subsequently, it was used with local audiences from public groups as part of presentations, refined with feedback, and shared for use in education and public engagement events.

3.4 Virtual Reality Demonstration Model

Interactive virtual reality demonstration models have been developed for two-way sharing knowledge, between citizens and the SHERPA teams, of approaches to tackling climate change and environmental sustainability through land use management practices. The models bring together information for two farms in north-east Scotland, UK, managed with land systems aiming to achieve climate positive impacts. The basing of such models on real places enables the narratives to be properly contextualised biophysically, economically and socially.

The land systems and management practices, and the observations and monitoring, are on the ground examples of building blocks within all four of the pillars of the Rural Action Plan. They include agroforestry, renewable energy, and agro-ecological practices which enhance soil health, protect waters, and the introduction of landscape features which increase biodiversity (e.g. [Balruddery Farm](#), Angus, UK). One site ([Glensaugh Farm](#), Aberdeenshire, UK) includes peatland restoration amongst its elements of a climate-positive farming initiative.

The contents and use of the models are designed to support the communication of SHERPA recommendation of Promoting existing good practices and virtuous examples of actions (e.g. multi-media demonstrations of best practices of just transition). Specific examples of alignment with building blocks in the Rural Action Plan are, in achieving **Resilient** rural areas of:

the role of a soil monitoring framework for measurements (e.g. digital sensors), in the delivery of A *soil deal for Europe*;

promoting peatland restoration actions as hubs for natural capital innovation, investment and economic activities, in delivery of *Addressing climate change in peatland areas through carbon farming*,

and in **Connected** rural areas of:

supporting digital solutions and technologies across agricultural activities and promoting the *digitalisation of the agricultural sector* (e.g. internet of things), in rural digital futures.

The models are designed for audiences of across all ages and backgrounds. They are designed to enable guided presentations and explanations of how land management can contribute to reducing GHG emissions, and self-navigation of models to explore the geography of the farms, and some of their characteristics (e.g. soils). The models have been augmented with datasets and features that relate to specific characteristics, such as before and after land use change (Figure 6 a, b), switching 'on and off' spatial data on soils, vegetation, aerial imagery and data derived from field observations such as levels of soil carbon (e.g. Figure 6 c).

The models use data feeds from the monitoring infrastructure, such as measurements of soil carbon and near real time monitoring of greenhouse gases on the ground and how such information can be reported, installed by the [NERC RETINA project](#) (Figure 7 a, b, c). These data have been translated them into imagery which can be viewed, interpreted and presented to citizens, stakeholder and policy audiences in a mobile virtual reality theatre (the [Virtual Landscape Theatre](#)) (Figure 8) and using headsets

The theatre environment enables group discussion about places, and audience inputs to their development, using interactive tools such as introducing new features (e.g. trees, wind turbines), and their positioning within the virtual environment by drag and drop functions. Additional information can be accessed by point and click to view multi-media features such as videos and viewing of the near real-time data feeds (Figure 6d). The headset environment provides individuals opportunities to explore areas of interest, navigating through the farm and linking to 360° videos from specific areas. Both environments can be run in venues in which audiences may feel more comfortable and at ease rather than them going to a research organisation or venue with which they are unfamiliar.

The medium and functionality of the virtual reality environments has proven to be attractive to all ages. For those in younger age groups the content and mechanisms align with educational curricula and in so doing contribute to the building block of *Encouraging education, training and employment opportunities for young people in rural areas*, in the **Prosperous** pillar of the Rural Action Plan.

3.5 Fiches on Governance of Rural Areas

The final topic tackled by the SHERPA MAPs was that of governance of rural areas. This covered the status of governance in the areas of the MAPs, existing interventions and recommendations, from which the position paper on [Empowering rural areas in multi-level governance processes](#) (Vilcu *et al.*, 2023) was derived. For this topic, each MAP prepared a position note (including several in languages other than English) accompanied by a two page fiche, with a total of 31 fiches prepared. The fiches contain the key

recommendations, strengths and needs, in an easily read format (e.g. Figure 9 a), and examples of good practice within the MAP areas (e.g. Figure 9 b).

The synthesis of the recommendations formed a key component of the finalised recommendations for future policies from SHERPA (D7.5), such as that under **Prosperous** rural areas of ...

strengthening the social economy, incentivising community empowerment and collaboration between municipalities to achieve an equitable green transition.

Figure 9 (a). Example of a fiche on governance in rural areas, from the Denmark MAP.

Figure 9 (b). Examples of good practice in governance from the German MAPs Nienburg, and Schleswig Holstein.

3.6 SHERPA Final video

As a final audio-visual output of the SHERPA project, a three-and-a-half-minute video was developed. The video contains an explanation on the implementation of the SHERPA process and present the key policy recommendations. It will be published on the project website before the end of November 2023. Some screenshots are provided below.

Figure 10(a). Screenshot from the final SHERPA video

Figure 10(b). Screenshot from the final SHERPA video

4. Example Activities with Citizens

4.1 Conference of the Parties (COP) 26

The approach and findings of SHERPA were deployed at high profile international events aligned to the topics debated by the MAPs. One example is the [Conference of the Parties on Climate Change \(COP 26\)](#), held in Glasgow, UK, November 2021. Approximately 40,000 people attended the negotiations in the Blue Zone, and 36,000 attended the public events in which SHERPA shared a stand with local partner, the James Hutton Institute, attended by partners and members of MAPs (Figure 10). Members of the public from around the world shared opinions on their priorities for tackling climate change, experiences of extreme weather events, and new business initiatives or food products using agro-ecological farming systems. They tested virtual reality models and 360° videos explaining peatland restoration, renewable energy, and climate change and water, watched the live panel sessions, or the broadcasts from the United Nations Blue Zone.

Those broadcasts covered agreements that “keep alive the Paris Agreement target of limiting global warming to 1.5°C”, implying a path to between 1.8°C and 2.4°C of warming, above the target of the Paris Agreement of 1.5°C but marking progress in aspects affecting rural areas. These included the [Declaration on Forests and Land Use](#), which refers to “promoting an inclusive rural transformation”, and building resilience, enhancing rural livelihoods and recognising the multiple values of forests; and the [Global Methane Pledge](#) to reduce global anthropogenic methane emissions across all sectors by at least 30% below 2020 levels by 2030 including the “abatement of agricultural emissions through technology innovation as well as incentives and partnerships with farmers”. These are also reflected in SHERPA recommendations under Rural Action Plan pillars of **Resilient** (Miller *et al.*, 2023, [SHERPA Climate Change and Land Use](#)) and **Connected** rural

areas (Arcuri, 2023; [SHERPA Digitalisation in rural areas](#)), such as the use of sensors for near real-time monitoring of GHG emissions from agricultural land.

The stand was also a hub for three live panel moderated Q&A sessions on Just Transitions to Climate Neutrality. One session was organised by SHERPA, focusing on 'How rural areas can contribute to a just transition to climate neutrality'. A moderated Panel and Question and Answer forum was held on the roles of agriculture, rural communities and social innovation for a [Just Transition to climate neutrality](#). The forum was [livestreamed from the COP venue](#), with over 70 attendees joined from across Europe, north and west Africa and Australia.

The SHERPA panellists argued that while travelling the pathways to climate neutrality, we need to be willing and have processes that learn from what goes wrong, and build positivity into messages of what can be achieved. Those processes should recognise that thinking needs to be integrated across sectors of society and industries, and that "knowledge is not only science", it also resides in the cumulative experiences gained through practice. They concluded that there is a need to lead by example, with effective science-society-policy interfaces, that are transparent and accessible to everyone, as reflected in SHERPA recommendations for policy to achieve the Rural Action Plan pillar of Stronger rural areas (Chartier *et al.*, 2023; D7.5), and associated research (Miller *et al.*, 2023b; [D7.4](#)).

4.2 European and National Rural Parliaments

The European Rural Parliament (ERP) "is a platform to link and express the voice of rural people in Europe and to promote self-help and action by rural people, in partnership with civil society and governments" ([European Rural Parliament](#), 2023). It collects information, ideas, case studies and policy suggestions from the rural population of Europe, using them as a basis for advocacy with European and national institutions. As such, this forum, and its national equivalents, provided one conduit to citizens and representatives of rural populations.

During the SHERPA project (October 2019 to September 2023) the mode of operation of the ERP was disrupted by the COVID-19 pandemic. As a result sessions were run, or contributed to, as online or hybrid events in 2021 and 2022. Presentations made by SHERPA, or with SHERPA participation, at:

1. Plenary presentation at the mid-term session of the European Rural Parliament on [Climate change - rural impacts, local action and policy](#) (27th October 2021);
2. Workshop session on [Rural trends, scenarios and solutions – views from 20 multi actor platforms](#), was moderated by representatives of [European Rural Development Network](#) (ERDN) at the European Rural Parliament biennial congress in Kielce, Poland (14th September 2022; Figure 11a).

Figure 12(a). Rural trends, scenarios and solutions – views from 20 multi-actor platforms (Chartier *et al.*,

Figure 12(b). European Connections session, Scottish Rural and Islands Parliament, 1st November

2021), a workshop at the European Rural Parliament, led by Barbara Wieliczko, and Katarzyna Gizińska, ERDN, from the Poland MAPs	2023, with panel session involving members of the EU level MAP, and the UK SHERPA team (James Hutton Institute).
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The national rural parliaments provide closer links to civil society and citizens in the regions and countries of their remit. In some countries, the SHERPA MAPs align closely to the areas of remit of the national rural parliaments (e.g. rural Scotland, UK). In Finland, the rural parliament was used as a forum for co-constructing the SHERPA position paper on [Change in Production and Diversification of the Rural Economy](#) (Martino *et al.*, 2022). The three workshops at the Finnish Rural Parliament were on:

1. [bioeconomy](#), 28 September 2021;
2. [entrepreneurship and new business models](#), 28 September 2021;
3. [smart rurality](#), 29 September 2021.

These three workshops, and a summary one held in Swedish, were used to share results from the draft Position Paper on Change in Production and Diversification of the Rural Economy of the Finnish MAP, and practice examples from Finland and the EU. Insights were also included from the MAPs in Denmark, Poland and Romania. The workshops identified and discussed needs and possibilities to improve economic diversification in rural areas and to develop recommendations. The output was the final Position Paper from the Finnish MAP ([Kull and Stjernberg, 2023](#)). Reflecting on the process and opportunity of engaging with the rural parliament in its Position Paper on Governance, the Finnish Map noted that ...

“To achieve a more holistic understanding of rural areas, policymakers and practitioners would benefit from more cross-sectoral learning. The Rural Parliament is an example of how this kind of learning and knowledge exchange can be promoted, as well as of horizontal and holistic execution.”([Stjernberg and Salonen, 2023](#)).

In the post-project period, contributions were made to two sessions of the [Scottish Rural and Islands Parliament](#) (Fort William, UK, 1st to 3rd November 2023). These sessions were on European Connections, and Cross-border issues, each covering themes of how to rural areas in Scotland can strengthen links to those in Europe, and the support mechanisms required, featuring SHERPA and its science, society, policy interfaces. The panel in the former session comprised representatives from the [European Rural Community Alliance](#) (ECRA), European Rural Parliament, and [Scottish Rural Action](#), who are members of the EU level MAP, and the UK SHEPRA team (James Hutton Institute). Two other members of the UK MAPs also participated (Figure 11 b).

4.3 European Week of Regions and Cities

SHERPA ran sessions at the European Week of Regions and Cities in 2022 and 2023. The European Week of Regions and Cities (EWRC), running since 2003, is described as a neutral forum which brings “together politicians, decision-makers, experts and practitioners of cohesion policy, as well as stakeholders from business, banking, civil society organisations, academia, the EU institutions and the media.” The EWRC contributes to the element of the SHERPA strategy of reaching out to citizens in Europe via municipalities and civil society organisations and forums in a position to attend such events in Brussels.

In 2022, a side event was run on [Effective Mechanisms To Address New Governance Challenges In European Rural Areas](#), jointly between the H2020 projects SHERPA and [POLIRURAL](#), as part of the Rural Cluster (8th November 2022). The session discussed new challenges for the governance of rural regions of Europe in times of almost continuous disruption, with four case studies were presented, two each from POLIRURAL and SHERPA, and opened by the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development of the Slovak Republic, Samuel Vlcan. The case studies from POLIRURAL were from Slovakia on a [National vision for more attractive rural areas](#), and Republic of Ireland with complimentary perspectives on [Planning for a vibrant rural future](#), and the SHERPA Danish MAP on [Sustainable Land Use – key for the Green Transition: Denmark Learnings](#),

Figure 11a) and [A SHERPA Multi-actor platform at regional level, take-aways for piloting EU projects in rural areas with rural people](#) (Figure 11b) presented by Samuel Féret, mayor of a French village and Monitor of two French SHERPA MAPs.

In 2023 contributions to the EWRC were through a session run by the [P10 MAP](#) in the Netherlands with partners [Wageningen University](#) and the [European Rural Development Network](#) on "[Participatory lab on the emancipation of rural areas in regional and urban policy](#)" (Figure 12); We're staying in rural areas: practices, policies and tools for thriving regions, with project [GRANULAR](#) and [Partenalia](#), and the EC organised "[Assessing the impact of Horizon 2020 funding on social innovation and going beyond](#)".

4.4 Education

In recommendations for policy (Chartier *et al.*, 2023, D7.5) and research (Miller *et al.*, 2023, D7.4) SHERPA identifies the need for a comprehensive strategy for developing human capital with training for teachers at primary, secondary and higher education levels, and Continuing Professional Development and life-long

learning linked to the use of Open Science and Open Data. Such a strategy aligns with the building blocks of the LTVRA **Stronger** pillar of *Supporting rural youth*, and of the **Prosperous** pillar of *Encouraging education, training and employment opportunities for young people in rural areas*.

The importance of raising understanding of issues facing rural areas is reflected in presentations to young people in rural areas in their education and training. For example, the [Schleswig Holstein MAP](#) ran workshops at which students developed their visions of rural areas in 2050 as part of their course, including their goals, projects, funding and implementation (Figure 13). The visions developed stressed the importance of early childhood education, highlighting needs for strengthening the practical relevance of school curricula and active cooperation of schools with land managers and rural entrepreneurs, and emphasising that addressing educational deficits on key issues facing rural areas is a prerequisite for fostering social innovations necessary to enhance capacities of rural communities to cooperate in environmental and climate protection.

Figure 15(a). Schleswig Holstein MAP running workshop on futures of rural areas; Fachhochschule Kiel, Germany.

Figure 15(b). Students presenting visions of rural areas by 2050; Fachhochschule Kiel, Germany.

Findings and recommendations from other individual MAPs and at SHERPA level are also being used in presentations in higher and further education by partners which have remits that include teaching and training (e.g. MSc course, [Geographic Information Systems](#), University of Aberdeen, UK, linking visioning for rural futures with the use of digital tools).

4.5 Events organised with and through Civil Society and MAPs

The remits and activities of organisations which are members of SHERPA MAPs provided opportunities for listening to public opinions on issues affecting rural areas and people, and sharing information on recommendations emerging from the SHERPA process. For example, the European Commission declared 2022 the [European Year of Youth](#). An aim was to profile the importance of Europe's young people in building a better, greener, more inclusive and more digital future. Members of the [Estonian MAP](#), at the Estonian Agricultural Research Centre, collected examples of projects supported by the Estonian Rural Development Plan 2014 to 2020 which involved young people. In September 2022 they ran an exhibition entitled "Entrepreneurial Rural Youth" of the projects to be shown in different regions of Estonia. The exhibition highlighted the participation of young people in agriculture and rural life with an aim of inspiring those of future generations ([Mändmets and Kärk, 2022](#)), and as such promoted the building block of [Supporting rural youth](#) under the **Stronger** pillar of the LTVRA.

Supporting rural youth is complemented by the building block in the **Prosperous** pillar of Encouraging education, training and employment opportunities for young people in rural areas. Those functions intersect the remits and activities of organisations which are members of MAPs though which opportunities were taken to convey messages and recommendations developed from their deliberations. For example, the [River Dee Catchment MAP](#) (UK) aligns with the [Dee Catchment Partnership](#) which attaches a significant importance to [outreach and education](#) to develop public understanding of sustainable land and river management.

The MAP organised or contributed to events for engaging with civil society, and citizens and their representatives at national and local levels. Events included those within the River Dee catchment or in its immediate vicinity (e.g. Living River Festival, Banchory, February 2020; Figure 14), explaining issues such as interventions to increase flood control, and reduce erosion of river beds and the loss of biodiversity, as highlighted in the [European Commission \(2021b\)](#) under one aspects of the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030. Events at Scottish level included demonstrations of water run-off in catchments with and without nature-based interventions and blue-green infrastructure (Figure 15).

Tools used at such events include physical models of hypothetical catchments with which to demonstrate how water flows through the catchment, and where and how physical interventions such as woodlands, peatland restoration and stream management can reduce flood risk, loss of soil and enhance the habitats of river courses (Figure 15). Such interventions were identified in the [SHERPA Position Paper on Climate Change and Environmental Sustainability](#) (Miller *et al.*, 2022) ([Climatically Friendly Villages Czechia MAP](#)) as important for mitigating effects of climate change and making positive contributions to improving habitats and biodiversity. As such they contribute to building blocks under the **Stronger, Resilient** and **Prosperous** pillars of the Rural Action Plan.

Figure 16(a). Hands-on model demonstrating erosion of river beds at the Living River Festival, Banchory, February 2020. (stand hosted by S Cooksley, Facilitator River Dee Catchment, right; Photograph D. Miller).

Figure 16(b; top, bottom). Exploring riverbank erosion with Tom Mason MSP, and citizens, 'Living River Festival', Banchory February 2020; photographs D. Miller).

Figure 17(a). Hands-on models of a catchment without (left) and with (right) interventions to management water flows (photograph D. Miller).

Figure 17(b). Demonstration catchments used in public event (Tarland, Aberdeenshire, March 2023; photograph S. Cooksley).

A [study visit](#) was run in the Kampinos National Park's buffer zone, by the local [Bieszczady Poland MAP](#) with the Traveler's Club, about the Bieszczady Mountains (22nd April 2023) (Figure 16 a). The audience comprised representatives of NGOs and local government, as well as photographers affiliated with the Union of Polish Nature Photographers (Figure 16 b). The focus of the event was on the findings of SHERPA on the [social dimension](#) of the Bieszczady Mountains and Leski poviats, presented by Katarzyna Gizińska (Figure 16 c, d). A specific SHERPA recommendation which emerged from this MAP, related to **Connected** rural areas, was on the creation of a mobile office to support rural e-services, going around neighbourhoods to enable residents to do administrative tasks directly from home and not have to travel to central venues ([Gizińska, 2022](#); [Černič Istenič, 2023](#); [SHERPA Social dimension of rural areas](#)).

The visit and event also reflected a recommendation from the MAP, prior to this event, of the value of exchanging experiences, reflected in the feedback of ...

"You know what, it wasn't until we went on a study visit that we saw how others can do such amazing things. Before, we thought we were masters at what we do. But this visit showed us that we still have a lot to learn." ([Bieszczady Poland MAP](#))

Figure 18(a). Study visit programme

Figure 18(b). Study visit attendees at Julinek Guesthouse, Kampinos National Park.

Figure 18(c). Katarzyna Gizińska presented SHERPA and findings of Bieszczady Poland MAP'

Figure 18(d). Characteristics of the area presented.

During the lock-downs of the COVID-19 pandemic such forms of communication and presentation were online. Tools such as Zoom, Teams and Webex became commonplace enabling ongoing engagement with

citizens through civil society events albeit at that time the experiences and protocols were new to many of the audiences and host organisations. Such events helped in developing early ideas of issues to consider in developing topics for deliberations by MAPs. They also appear to have fulfilled a role of providing content to processes of communities of interest and place in maintaining forms of continuity of social engagement during lock-downs and constraints on in-person meeting.

4.6 Broadcast and digital media

Other contributions to discussions about issues affecting rural areas and people with citizens included mass media of conventional broadcasting and online streaming of radio and television interviews. Examples include the Agro TV, programme "[Agriculture - a chance for Romania](#)", featuring M. Tudor, Romanian Academy Institute of Agricultural Economics and ERDN (26th July 2023).

News and magazine coverage also included national and local radio stations. For example, four members of the Iași Romania MAP and partner ERDN (Monica Tudor, S. Bruma, F. Arion and D. Badea) were interviewed for an hour on the Romanian national radio station Radio Antena Satelor about the results of SHERPA. The particular focus was on the sustainability of agro-food value chains (<https://www.facebook.com/RadioAntenaSatelor/videos/244038955268305>). The topic enabled findings from the Iași Romania MAP, [Towards sustainable and resilient value chains](#) (Vasiliu *et al.*, 2022).

5. Conclusions

Engaging with citizens has been an integral part of the four year programme of work of SHERPA. This respects the significance of their participation in discourse about visions for rural areas, as per the Treaty on the European Union ([European Union, 2012](#)), and enablers for them to be realised.

The SHERPA strategy for engaging with citizens of Europe through different channels, conscious of the importance of ensuring the local relevance of messages (e.g. in the content and places for use of videos; topics covered in media interviews; digital and analogue exhibits). The processes of citizen engagement exposed partners to perspectives, evidence, suggestions, criticisms and feedback on recommendations which are not otherwise captured within the network of MAPs. That was part of a structured, bottom-up approach to the preparation of regional and national, and SHERPA level Position Papers, into which citizens have had direct or indirect inputs. Ultimately, the output from the process was sets of recommendations for future rural policies ([Miller *et al.*, 2022c, D7.3](#); [Chartier *et al.*, 2023; D7.5](#)) and research priorities ([Chartier *et al.*, 2022, D7.2](#); [Miller *et al.*, 2023b, D7.4](#)).

The materials designed primarily for citizen engagement provide a valuable set of legacy materials that can be expanded upon as contexts evolve (e.g. storymap, virtual reality models, videos). Several items (e.g. fiches on governance, videos, and broadcast media, are in languages other than English. These materials are open for viewing and use, and thus also remain available to the 22 MAPs which will continue as active science-society-policy interfaces for engaging rural actors in policy and rural development post-SHERPA ([Potters *et al.*, 2023, D6.4](#)).

Reaching out to citizens through third parties of civil society and MAPs was designed to amplify the messages by exploiting their membership, connections and communications mechanisms. This considerably reduced the overheads associated with relying on project partners and resources, and broadened the contexts for engagement. As noted by [Potters *et al.* \(2023, D6.4\)](#), "*the MAP process strengthens the engagement of citizens and the building of local capacity to engage in policy processes.*" Feedback from organisations involved in such collaborations appears to confirm the benefits of the approach to all parties in achieving their aims and delivering within their remits.

The processes and outputs of the SHERPA science-society-policy interfaces facilitated pertinent contributions of citizens into policy making. The significance of such perspectives and inputs is reflected in the [European Commission \(2020\)](#) observation that "the volatility of evidence, uncertainty of today and tomorrow's facts

requires mobilising all citizens to share not only relevant knowledge but also responsibility on the governance of the current crises.”

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